

IN-HABIT - INclusive Health And wellBeing In small and medium size ciTies

D8.3 IN-HABIT WEBSITE

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Authors (names and affiliations)	E. Silvestri, C. Cecinelli, C. Marrone, S. Marrone, D. Bordin Book on a Tree		

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VERSION HISTORY

Version	Status	Date	Contributor/partner	Summary of changes
V 0.1	Draft/	24/08/2021	E. Silvestri Cecinelli, C. Marrone, S. Marrone (BOT)	Initial drafting
V 0.2	Draft /	30/08/2021	E. Silvestri Cecinelli, C. Marrone, S. Marrone, D. Bordin (BOT)	Advanced draft
V 0.3	Final document	31/08/2021	BOT	Feedback included, language final revision

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1. INTRODUCTION

1.1 Deliverable description

This document outlines the **development** of the INclusive Health And wellBeing In small and medium size ciTies (IN-HABIT) **website** – WP8 Dissemination, Exploitation, Communication and Outreach strategy (DECO) – deliverable D8.3 of Task 8.2 (communication and engagement actions and tools), with a focus on the **creation and amelioration of the project website**. The functioning website has been online since M12 (September 2021).

The ultimate goal is to produce a multilingual, user-friendly and easy-to-navigate space to **enhance public awareness** and **promote local events**, news and results through a recognisable and strong visual identity based on the project's communication guidelines, as long as a recognizable dynamic space to disseminate project progress and results.

The website represents a **multilingual modular communication platform** whose purpose is to be used by city partners to **promote visionary and integrated solutions (VIS)**, by disseminating project updates, news, events, results and products. The website will be integrated with the IN-HABIT platform and app and will embed social media news feeds throughout the project lifetime.

After the confirmation and development of the visual identity of the project on M6, and following the first release of the landing page, feedback from Project Partners (PPs) has been carefully

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collected during meetings with the communication representatives and through ad hoc surveys about the content and structure of the website.

A totally **new, significantly improved version of the website**, has been developed and shared with PPs in July 2021, taking into account their suggestions on a collaborative and collated feedback approach. The new website also responds to the suggestions of the project advisor (PA) and Commission for a more dynamic, yet clear vehicle of information and dissemination.

The website can be reached at www.inhabit-h2020.eu and will be subject to regular updates as the project progresses.

1.2 Technical features

The website www.inhabit-h2020.eu has been created and managed using the web publishing software WordPress, version 5.8, and is available on computers and mobile devices alike. After an initial landing page had been developed in M6 to allow project communication purposes, a new, enhanced version has been adapted to fit the project's needs and delivered in M10 (July 2021).

The plugin WP User Frontend Pro (<https://wedevs.com/wp-user-frontend-pro/>) makes it possible to create a **Reserved Area** that is only accessible to users with the role of *partners*, who will be able to upload and download files that are not available to common users, as stated in the Project Handbook (§ 3.3.3 Information and Communication Structure). The website is **GDPR**

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compliant thanks to the use of the GDPR Cookie consent plugin CookieYes | GDPR Cookie Consent & Compliance Notice (<https://www.webtoffee.com/product/gdpr-cookie-consent/>).

In particular, the privacy policy and the cookie policy have been carefully reviewed with the support of a legal team of experts, and documents of reference can be found [here](#) and [here](#).

The website security is ensured by the plugin WordFence (<https://it.wordpress.org/plugins/wordfence/>), which blocks the attacks attempted by remote hosts and ensures the safety of the server and the installed plugins.

2. WEBSITE STRUCTURE

2.1 General structure

The IN-HABIT website's main structure has been defined and confirmed and comprises two parts:

- A **public area to raise awareness** and guarantee the visibility of the IN-HABIT project as well as to **encourage the participation** of stakeholders and local inhabitants through the publication of project updates and news and the promotion of local initiatives.
- A **reserved area** that only project partners will be able to access in order to **share files and useful documents** that might not be open access.

All sections of the website feature the IN-HABIT logo in the top-left corner and the main contact information and indication of the funding received by the European Union's Horizon 2020

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research and innovation programme at the bottom, in compliance with the European Commission guidelines on the matter.

A site map can be found at: <https://www.inhabit-h2020.eu/site-map/>

2.2 The public area

At the moment, the public area comprises the following sections (pages and subpages):

Homepage

About

The project

Objectives

Roadmap/Work Plan

Outcomes

Cities

Cordoba

Lucca

Nitra

Riga

Partners

Project Partners

Sister projects

Resources

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Media & Press

Scientific publications

Deliverables

Research activities

Newsletter

News & Events

News

Events

Reserved Area

Contacts

3. RELEASES

A **roadmap** for progressing towards the functioning website in M12 had been established, and implemented, setting out the releases planned.

1st release

The table below outlines how the **content** of the pages has been organized in the **first release**, implemented with the project partners' cooperation **by the end of February/start of March 2021**, M6 (first release):

Section	Content
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HOME	The landing page. Featuring: a slider with photos of the four cities; a timeline outlining the milestones of the projects; a calendar space; a social media feed; a grid menu; a list of the project partners identified by their names and clickable logos.
MEDIA & NEWS	The Media & News page, two sub-sections: News & Press and Media & Resources. News & Press is the space where the Press Review documents would be periodically uploaded and made available to the public, whereas Media & Resources would host multimedia content, such as videos and podcasts, to be defined consistently with the project DECO – Dissemination and Communication plan – as the project develops.
CITIES	The page contains clickable maps/photos through which the user will be redirected to the sub-pages dedicated to the four cities: Nitra, Riga, Lucca and Cordoba.
City of Nitra	Each of the sub-pages dedicated to the cities opens with a photo and a short introductory text both in English and in the local language. A calendar provides information about local events and news linked to the project.
City of Riga	
City of Lucca	
City of Cordoba	
PROJECT PARTNERS	The page would list all the project partners and identify them with their logos which, when clicked on, allow users direct access to the PP's website or social media channels.
ABOUT	The project's objectives and main information is presented thanks to an easy-to-read infographic accompanied by concise blocks of English text.

Table 1. Website page content changes planned for the first release.

2nd release

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A second release, in accordance with the PPs as above mentioned, was implemented in April-June 2021 (M8-M10) and shared in July 2021. It featured:

- Better organised content;
- Upload of milestone timeline and relevant infographics;
- Use of icons and illustrations;
- Completion of the PP profiles;
- Easier way to consult the press review, the deliverables and the scientific publications sections;
- A space manageable by the community activators in the local language added to the city sub-pages;
- Fully-functional calendar and events space;
- Greater use of the IN-HABIT icons to strengthen the visual identity;
- Enhanced social media feeds.

Pages	Sub-pages	Content	Responsible Users (Content Input)
HOME		The landing page. Featuring: a slider with and introductory slide followed by a photo of each of the cities (five slides in total); a brief introduction of the projects accompanied by the four official city icons; a short text outlining the core ideas behind the project (health, wellbeing, inclusiveness, replication); a short description of the four cities and on what IN-HABIT	BOT

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		will focus on in the area; an Events section; a list of the project partners identified by their names and clickable logos; a social media feed.	
ABOUT	The project Objectives Roadmap/Work Plan Outcomes	An introductory page that features clickable official IN-HABIT icons linked to the four sub-pages. The aim of this section is to explain what the project focuses on, how it intends to operate, which are the main milestones and work packages and what it is expected to achieve.	BOT/All PPs
CITIES	Cordoba Lucca Nitra Riga	The main page contains: a short introductory text; a map with placeholders for each of the cities that take part in the project; the four clickable city icons linked to the sub-pages of Nitra, Riga, Lucca and Cordoba. Each page opens with a photo and a short introductory text, both in English and in the local language. A blog section managed by the KLCs provides information on local events and news.	LCAs (Local Community Activators) and KLCs (Key Local Contacts)
PARTNERS	Project Partners Sister Projects	There's no introductory page in this case. The sub-page Project Partners lists all the partners with their logos. When clicked on, the logo takes the user to	BOT/All PPs/ Sister project representatives

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		<p>the PP's website. To read the PP's profile, the user can click on the button "Find out more" under the logo.</p> <p>The sub-page Sister Projects provides an overview of Horizon 2020 projects similar to IN-HABIT and it features their logos, a short description and the option to be redirected to their websites through the button "Visit Website".</p>	
RESOURCES	<p>Media & Press</p> <p>Scientific publications</p> <p>Deliverables</p> <p>Research activities</p> <p>Newsletter</p>	<p>The main page features a short text and four of the IN-HABIT official icons, each linked to one of the sub-pages.</p> <p>The sub-page Media & Press collects all the available IN-HABIT material: leaflet, brochure, videos, press releases and review articles.</p> <p>The sub-page Research Activities features surveys about the cities, available in English and in the local languages.</p>	BOT/All PPs/Research partners
NEWS & EVENTS	<p>News</p> <p>Events</p>	<p>The introductory page features two of the official IN-HABIT icons linked to the sub-page News and the sub-page Events and a social media feed.</p>	BOT/All PPs/LCAs and KLCs
RESERVED AREA		<p>An area reserved to project partners and used to store documents regarding the</p>	BOT/All PPs

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		project that cannot be shared with the general public.	
CONTACTS		A page which collects the email addresses that can be used to contact the different people who work on the project.	BOT

Table 2. Website page content, present (second release).

3.1 The landing page and homepage - focus on

The first version of the website’s landing page, like the rest of the website, was activated in the final months of 2020, anticipating the delivery due date at M4 of the project. It acted as a **tool and window for the project** for the Kick-off Meeting held in October 2020, carefully following the style guide to create a **well-defined visual identity** through the use of the IN-HABIT logo, colours and background patterns.

Following actions planned for M6, February 2021, include an update of the website’s main sections, following the release plan shared at the Project Partners’ meeting on 12th January, 2021. The sections were improved in order to be **better organised**, both visually and from a content point of view, and **easier to navigate**.

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Figure 1. Screenshot of the homepage, present.

The improved landing page includes the following enhanced features:

- A **visually enhanced slider** to immediately draw attention to the four cities and the key elements of the project;
- A **short text** explaining what the project is about, completed with the four city icons;
- Four paragraphs outlining the project's main ideas: health, wellbeing, inclusiveness, replication.
- A **section dedicated to the cities** completed with a brief description of how and on which aspects IN-HABIT will operate in the area, the city icons and professional photographs that relate to the project.
- An **events section** updated with the upcoming IN-HABIT events.

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- A grid with the **logos of the Project Partners**, clickable and linked to their official websites.
- A **social media feed** to attract the users' attention to the latest news and encourage them to take an active part in the programme.

3.2 The city pages - focus on

The sub-pages dedicated to the four cities were changed and updated as part of the next release makeover.

Figure 2. Screenshot, City of Cordoba sub-page, present.

This release has seen the following elements added:

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- A **visual element** of the city to ameliorate the experience, draw the users' attention and put the project into context; more information about the city development projects and solutions, including, if possible, visual elements of the areas involved in the regeneration interventions (maps, etc.);
- An **introductory text** translated into the local language, followed by a button to download the city leaflet.
- Some of the **IN-HABIT icons** related to the work that will be done in the city, strengthening the project's visual identity.
- A **space manageable by the community activators** to help engage the locals by sharing news and events that will take place in the area;

4. USE OF ICONS AND IMAGERY

The project visual identity has been incorporated on the website through the use of icons, a distinctive trait of the project's visuals. The icons allow immediate communication and a friendly, easy-to-use interface.

Infographics have also been utilized in order to include complex information in simpler representations, and to convey project information wherever available. Finally, the use of illustrations has allowed us to offer a friendlier, immediate approach.

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5. ACCESSIBLE VERSION

The website has been adapted for disadvantaged public, allowing various accessibility modes through a button in every page:

- Epilepsy Safe Mode: dampens color and removes blinks;
- Visually Impaired Mode: improves website's visuals;
- Cognitive Disability Mode: helps to focus on specific content;
- ADHD Friendly Mode: reduces distractions and improve focus;
- Blindness Mode: allows using the site with screen-readers.

6. FURTHER RELEASES & EXPLORATIONS

The second year of the project will see the implementation of another additional release, as follows:

Release	Update
Third release – October 2021- March 2022 release (M14-M18)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Fully working Reserved area to support the relevant communication actions; • Upgrade of the Media page; • Special section (or redirect) for children and schools (to be defined); • A place for local grassroots initiatives (to be defined); • Resources section for cooperation and synergies with partners.

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Table 3. Timings and content planned for the third release.

Figure 3. Timeline of website release (3).

7. COLLABORATION WITH PROJECT PARTNERS

It is important to strengthen and continue driving **efficient and effective collaboration** with PPs. In order to do so, BOT is periodically in touch with the partners to make sure the visibility of the project, as well as the integration with the DECO plan, are ensured. Some key actions for which the collaboration between BOT and the project partners is fundamental are:

- **Collecting articles or newsletters** that are relevant to the project;
- **Creating a mailing list** with all the relevant organisations and entities at a local as well as an EU/topic/theme level;

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- **Listing all the events** that need to be added to the calendar sections on the website and advertised on the IN-HABIT social media channels;
- **Collecting information** on who will deal with local institutional communication and who will translate/approve the documents in the local languages so that a collaboration process can be continued and strengthened.

Official IN-HABIT email addresses have been created and activated for the key local contacts (KLCs) and the Project Communication manager, who have already received their credentials. The addresses have been added to the Contacts page on the website, along with that of the Project Coordinator (PC), who already had an existing domain at the University of Cordoba dedicated to project coordination.

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Figure 2. Screenshot, City of Cordoba subpage, present.

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English	Spanish
	<p>City of Cordoba Culture and heritage hub</p> <p>Located in the south of Spain, the city has a long history and contributes to the cultural and historical heritage. Cordoba faces environmental problems such as unemployment and the water crisis, and has been recognized as a European Green Capital in 2014.</p> <p>INHABIT action: Heritage & Culture Area of Impact: Local Communities</p> <p>What is the project looking for? Encouraging the use of culture and heritage in the promotion of innovation, digital and startups, and public spaces. In Cordoba, a digital marketplace, based on existing data, will be created to promote local initiatives. Such as mobile learning, heritage, tourism, employment opportunities and business incubation, with specific goals and relevant strategies to reach and connect to local communities.</p>

Figure 3. Timeline of website release (3).

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